

MANAGEMENT AND ITS MODERN METHODS

Professor of the Department of Economics, Renaissance University of
Management

Khodzhamuratova Gulbakhar Yuldashevna

Annotation: This article examines the essence of systemic management and its importance in modern management systems. A systemic management approach is a way of considering an organization as a holistic system, connecting all its parts with each other and striving to achieve common goals. The article analyzes the basic principles, methodology and application of systemic management in practice. A systemic approach allows managers to effectively manage relationships between different departments of the organization, properly allocate resources, optimize processes and improve results. The article also examines the compatibility of modern management with systemic approaches, its importance in strategic management, innovative technologies and increasing competitiveness. It helps to develop effective management strategies for organizations by analyzing the role of systems management in achieving long-term success, as well as the technological tools and methodologies that support systematic decision-making.

Keywords: Systems management, modern management, management system, strategic management, innovative technologies, systems approach, resource management, efficiency, decision-making, competitiveness, management methodology, systems theory

Management is a method of ensuring the work process in an integrated and coordinated manner to achieve specific goals through the effective use of current resources. Management helps to achieve organizational goals effectively and efficiently by planning, organizing, staffing, directing, and controlling organizational resources. At the most fundamental level, management is a discipline that consists of five general functions:

- planning, organizing, staffing, leading, and controlling. These five functions are part of a set of practices and theories for becoming a successful manager.

• Understanding the functions helps managers focus their efforts on activities that will produce results. Summary of the Five Functions of Senior Management (ICPM Management Content): Planning: When you think of planning in a management role, it refers to the process of selecting appropriate goals and actions, then deciding what strategies to use, what actions to take, and what resources are needed to achieve the goals. Organizing: This is the process of establishing working relationships that allow employees to work together to achieve their organizational goals. Leading: This function involves expressing a vision, empowering employees, seeing, influencing, persuading, and inspiring and motivating people using effective communication skills. Staffing: Recruiting and selecting employees for positions within the company (within teams and departments). Controlling: This is likely to be the process of evaluating how well you are achieving your goals, improving performance, and implementing actions. The method of organizational forms is often used in management when situations begin to change suddenly or gradually. In this case, it is also necessary to sort out and select methods that are suitable for the situation. In management practice, methods are mainly used simultaneously. In this case, the methods used are combined. It should be noted that there are no instructions or recommendations that meet the standard requirements for classifying management methods in the economy according to their content or tasks. Because management does not operate in a synchronous manner. This is especially evident in an economy based on market relations. As market relations or consumer preferences for market products begin to change, many methods in management merge, sometimes negating each other, sometimes supporting each other. In such situations, the use of additional methods is also required. Management helps in the effective utilization of skills and knowledge of professionals and specialists to reduce labor, material and all related direct and indirect costs. Management enables the industry to maximize the utilization of resources by selecting the best alternative use. If the resources you use in terms of investment, transportation, labor, etc. are recorded and calculated in advance, there is no reason for the increase in costs. Better

still, it helps the organization in the efficient utilization of labor and machinery and thus helps in reducing costs. Management as a function is responsible for the growth and survival of the organization. Management helps organizations to adapt to the changing market demand/changing needs of the societies.

Thus, it helps them to thrive even when they experience changes in market trends. Management fills various positions with the right people with the right skills, training and qualifications. All jobs should be open to everyone. The sign of a good management system for an organization is that it helps the organization to function well financially, as a team and as individuals. Resources are coordinated, directed and controlled in such a way that the enterprise works towards achieving its goals. By clearly defining the purpose of the organization, time, money and effort are not wasted.

Management is essential for any organization that wants to be effective and achieve its goals. As we have already mentioned, management has four main functions - planning, organizing, leading and controlling. Without these principles of management, the organization may face difficulties in achieving its goals in the first place! The classic theory on the principles of management was written by Henry Fayol. He tried to divide management into 14 principles. Having a clear management structure is essential for any successful organization. The approach of managers tends to filter through the entire organization, so exemplary performance by managers sets a good example for employees.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. “Qonun ustuvorligi va inson manfaatlarini ta’minlash – yurt taraqqiyoti va xalq farovonligi garovi” mavzusidagi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi qabul qilinganining 24 yilligiga bag‘ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi ma’ruzasi. – T.: “O‘zbekiston”, 2017.
2. Djurayev R.X., Turg‘unov S.T. Ta’lim menejmenti. –T.: Voris-nashriyot, 2006. - 259 b.
3. Djurayev R.X., Turg‘unov S.T. Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim tashkilotlarini boshqarishda

menejmentning asosiy tushunchalari. –T.: Fan, 2006.

4. [https://www.uagc.edu/blog/5-principles-of-great-management#:~:text=At%20the%20most%20fundamental%20level,%20staffing%2C%20leadi ng%20and%20controlling.](https://www.uagc.edu/blog/5-principles-of-great-management#:~:text=At%20the%20most%20fundamental%20level,%20staffing%2C%20leadi%20ng%20and%20controlling.)

5.

6. <https://www.mygreatlearning.com/blog/what-is-management-definitions-and-functions/>